

The Main Symptoms and Clinical Manifestations of Coronavirus Disease in Children: A Descriptive Minireview

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ABSTRACT

Coronaviruses (coronaviruses) are a large family of viruses that cause diseases in both humans and animals. It is known that the emerging corona affects the respiratory system in addition to other more serious diseases such as the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). Recently, a new type of corona virus appeared and caused the death of many around the world, and it is still continuing until now, as it claimed the lives of millions of people and infected more than 200 million around the world. Infection of children with the virus usually causes an infection in the upper respiratory tract, which is accompanied by symptoms and signs similar to those that appear when infection with other viral infections such as influenza and cold symptoms.

KEYWORDS: SARS, Coronavirus disease

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INTRODUCTION

Corona virus (English: Coronaviruses) is known as one of the coronaviruses, and it was named in relation to the appendages on the surface of these viruses that resemble a crown in their shape, and these viruses affect the respiratory system of mammals, including humans, in addition to the possibility of corona viruses affecting the intestine sometimes. It should be noted that there are seven known human types of corona viruses so far, differing from each other in the severity of the disease and its spread, and there are four types that are common among members of society and cause diseases that are not often dangerous, and in fact, 15-30% of cold diseases spread among individuals. It is the result of viral infection with one of the common corona viruses, while the rare and dangerous types that may cause death are the corona virus known as MERS-CoV, which causes the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus, which first appeared in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in 2012, and the SARS-CoV virus that causes severe acute respiratory syndrome (English: Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona) navirus), which first appeared in China in 2002, in addition to the new Corona virus 2019, which appeared in China at the end of 2019.

INITIATION OF CORONAVIRUS SYMPTOMS

Symptoms of infection begin to appear 2-14 days after exposure to the virus, and the disease can be distinguished by the following symptoms: Pain in the joints of the body. general fatigue headache. Sore throat. Visibly elevated body temperature. Cough and difficulty breathing. Severe inflammation and damage to the alveoli. Swelling of lung tissue. Kidney failure if symptoms worsen. Corona disease may lead to death in case of neglect and exacerbation of symptoms; Because the virus that causes the disease prevents oxygen from reaching the blood, causing a deficiency in the activities of the body's organs.

COMMON SYMPTOMS OF CORONA VIRUS

During their lifetime, most individuals are infected with one of the common types of human coronaviruses, which appear in the form of mild to moderate symptoms in the upper respiratory tract often, and these symptoms are a runny nose, headache, cough, sore throat, fever, and general fatigue in the body, as well as These symptoms usually disappear within a short period, and in fact, these viruses can sometimes cause lower respiratory infections; Such as: pneumonia and bronchitis, in some groups of society; Such as: the elderly,

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infants, individuals with weak immunity, and those with heart and lung diseases.

SYMPTOMS OF CORONA VIRUS IN CHILDREN

Corona virus has been known since the 1960s, but at that time the infection of children with the virus was not accompanied by concerns about suffering from serious complications; As the virus usually causes an infection in the upper respiratory tract (English: Upper Respiratory Tract Infection), which is accompanied by symptoms and signs similar to those that appear when infection with other viral infections such as influenza, and these symptoms usually disappear alone within several days. Lower respiratory tract infection (English: Lower Respiratory Tract Infection): Pneumonia and bronchitis are uncommon in children in general, but infection with the Corona virus may be associated with serious health complications in newborns, Or children born early, or with less than normal weight, or those who suffer from other health problems, and it should be noted that infection with the Corona virus may lead to the emergence of some symptoms and signs in other organs of the body, in addition to pulmonary symptoms and signs, and the following is a statement of some Among the most important symptoms and signs associated with infection in general: [2] [3] sneezing. Runny nose. Fatigue and tiredness. coughing; High temperature. sore throat. Exacerbation of asthma. Abdominal pain. vomiting. diarrhea. Effects on the central nervous system (in English: Central Nervous System). It is noteworthy that the symptoms may vary from person to person, in some cases the infection may pass without symptoms, and in other cases it may be severe so that it poses a threat to the life of the patient.

PREVENTION METHODS

It is advised to take care to follow the necessary preventive measures to avoid infection with one of the Corona viruses, because in fact there is no vaccine against these viruses, and the most important preventive instructions are the following: [6] Maintaining clean hands by washing them well with warm water and soap, or using a hand sanitizer containing on alcohol. Avoid contact of hands and fingers with eyes, nose and mouth. Avoid close contact with people infected with the Coronavirus.

TREATMENT

The treatment of coronavirus is similar to the treatment of the common cold; Where the symptoms of the disease are alleviated by following the following tips: [6] Get enough rest and sleep. Drink enough fluids. Use of over-the-counter sore throat and fever medicines that relieve pain, such as; Acetaminophen (English: Acetaminophen), and ibuprofen (English: Ibuprofen). Use a humidifier, or make a steam bath to relieve a sore and itchy throat.

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